

Development And Validation of Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method for The Quantitative Determination of Iguratimod in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

The Development of a simple, precise and accurate RP-HPLC method for the determination of Iguratimod in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form and the developed method was validated as per the ICH Q2(R1) guidelines. A Shimadzu C18 Column (4.5×250 mm, 5 µm) and the Mobile phase of Methanol: Acetonitrile: HPLC Water (30:30:40 v/v/v) was used for separation and quantification of Iguratimod. Analyses were carried out by flow rate of 1 ml/min at the detection wavelength 258 nm. This method covers the linearity range of 10-50 µg/ml with the Correlation co-efficient (r²) was 0.9999. The System suitability parameters were within the acceptable limits. The Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) were found to be 1.2188 µg/ml and 3.6933 µg/ml respectively. The mean % recovery was found to be 99.86 ± 0.4909 %. Further the samples were studied under different stress conditions includes acid, base, hydrolytic, oxidative, reduction, photolytic, thermal and UV-light degradation studies. These Forced degradation studies confirms that there was no interference were found in Drug Iguratimod. Hence, The developed method was successfully applied for the routine quality control assay of Iguratimod in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form, as well as applied for quantification of Drug under various stress conditions.

Keywords: Iguratimod, RP-HPLC method, Analytical method development, Stability-indicating methods.

INTRODUCTION

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) also known as High-Pressure Liquid Chromatography, is a type of column chromatography which is commonly used in biochemistry for the analysis in order to separate, identify, and quantify components. It is a popular analytical technique for separating, identifying, and quantifying each components of a mixture. HPLC is a sophisticated column liquid chromatography technology [1]. HPLC is the most accurate analytical methods predominantly used for the quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis of both drug substance and drug product as well as for assessing the stability of the drug product. In HPLC, the prepared sample solution is introduced into a column packed with the porous material (stationary phase), while the mobile phase (solvent system) is pumped at higher pressure through

the column. The principle of separation occurs based on the adsorption of solute molecules to the stationary phase depends on its affinity towards the stationary phase [2].

Types of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography

a) Normal phase HPLC

b) Reversed phase HPLC [3]

HPLC method development involves several crucial steps like, pretreatment of sample, Detection of sample bands, selection of chromatographic conditions, quantitation and method validation with column, eluent, operational parameters makes high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method development become sophisticated [4-9].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Iguratimod is Anti-Rheumatic Drug, used for the treatment of Rheumatoid arthritis and it was developed by Toyama chemical company. The Drug Iguratimod was approved in Japan. Iguratimod molecular formula is $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_6S$. Its chemical name is N-[7-(methanesulfonamido)-4-oxo-6-phenoxychromen-3yl] formamide and Molecular weight is 374.367 g/mol^[10]. Its melting point is 238-242 °C^[11]. Iguratimod capable of inhibiting nuclear factor-kappa B (NF-κB) from the cytoplasm to the nucleus. This occurs without affecting the degradation of Ikappa Balpa in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated THP-1 cells (human monocytic leukemia cell line)^[12].

Figure-1: Structure Of Iguratimod^[13]

An attempt was made to develop simple, precise and accurate analytical method for routine quality control and assessing the stability of the drug (Iguratimod) under different stress conditions by Reversed-phase High-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) and Validate the method as per ICH guidelines.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Instrumentation

Analysis carried out by Shimadzu double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model UV-1700), Shimadzu HPLC system (C_{18} 4.5×250 mm, 5 μm), Lab solution HPLC software, Shimadzu HPLC system LC-20AD. Shimadzu AUX-220 Electronic balance for weighing the sample, Ultrasonic cleaner (2100 MH) for Sonication and InfraDIGI-250 °C Hot air oven were used for this method.

Chemicals and Reagents

Iguratimod API was purchased as gift sample from Chennai. Tablet formulation of Iguratimod-25 mg were purchased from Medplus.

HPLC grade Methanol, Acetonitrile and Water.

Chemicals such as 0.1 N H_2SO_4 , 0.1 N KOH, HPLC grade water, 0.3 % Hydrogen peroxide, 10 % Sodium bisulfate.

RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Selection of mobile phase

Methanol, Acetonitrile, Water were the three solvents selected as Mobile phase for Iguratimod.

Optimization of mobile phase

The selected mobile phase was tried in different ratios to get sharp chromatographic peak. There were several trials was conducted for Iguratimod in order to select the suitable mobile phase, mobile phase ratio, column, diluent and flowrate for Optimized Peak.

Table-1: Optimization Of Mobile Phase

Si.No	Mobile Phase	Column	Ratio	Flow rate	Solvent	Remarks
1	MeOH : ACN : Water (C_{18} 4.6×250 mm, 5 μm)	Shimadzu	25:15:60 % v/v/v	1 ml/min	MeOH	No peak
2		Shimadzu	40:40:20 % v/v/v	1 ml/min	MeOH	Peak sharp but early tailing
3		Phenomenox	30:30:40 % v/v/v	1 ml/min	MeOH	Peak splitted
4		Shimadzu	30:30:40 % v/v/v	1 ml/min	MeOH	Peak sharp with extra peak
5		Shimadzu	30:30:40(0.1%formic acid in water) % v/v/v	1 ml/min	MeOH	Peak was came with tailing
6		Shimadzu	30:30:40 % v/v/v	1 ml/min	Mobile phase	The Optimized Peak

Preparation of Mobile phase

The HPLC grade Solvents such as Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water were mixed properly in the ratio of 30:30:40 % v/v/v. Then, this solution was sonicated for 15 mins and which was filtered by using 0.22 μm membrane filter for removing the impurities.

Preparation of Diluent

The mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Preparation of Standard stock solution

The Standard stock solution of Igaratimod was prepared by weighed accurately 25 mg of standard and transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask and made up to the volume with diluent (mobile phase) containing 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration. From this, 5 ml was pipetted into 50 ml volumetric flask and made up to the volume with diluent containing 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (standard stock solution). The working standard was prepared from standard stock solution.

Detection of wavelength

Igaratimod was prepared in Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water (30:30:40 % v/v/v) scanned in the UV range 400-200 nm. The spectrum of Igaratimod showed the maximum absorbance at 258 nm for Present research work.

Optimized Chromatographic conditions

In RP-HPLC, Isocratic mode of elution was selected. Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water in the ratio of 30:30:40 % v/v/v were the mobile phase with the flowrate of 1 ml/min. Ambient Column temperature was maintained throughout the study. The sample injection volume was 20 μl . The run was 10 mins. The detected wavelength for Igaratimod was found as 258 nm.

Table-2: Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Mode of Operation	Isocratic mode
Stationary phase	Shimadzu C ₁₈ column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water (30:30:40 % v/v/v)
Detection wavelength	258 nm
Diluent	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water (30:30:40 % v/v/v)
Flow rate	1 ml/min
Temperature	Ambient temperature
Sample volume	20 μl

Estimation of Marketted Formulation

Twenty tablets were taken, crushed and powdered. Accurately weighed the powder equivalent to 25mg of iguratimod and transferred into 25ml of volumetric flask dissolved by using diluent and sonicated for 15 mins. The flask was shaken well and the volume was diluted up to the mark with diluent. The above solution was filtered by using the whatman filter paper. Further 5 ml was pipetted from the above solution and transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask with diluent upto the mark. Then, 1ml of the above solution was pipetted and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask using diluent to made upto the mark to get the concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution and this was used for routine analysis of Igaratimod formulation in RP-HPLC system.

RP-HPLC METHOD VALIDATION ^[14]

a) System suitability

The system suitability parameters were performed by injecting the standard Igaratimod solution in HPLC system. The parameters like Capacity factor, theoretical plate number and tailing factor was within the acceptable limits.

b) Linearity

The linearity of Igaratimod were prepared by pipetting 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml from the 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ standard stock solution and transferred into five 10 ml volumetric flasks separately and made up to the volume with diluent to obtain the concentrations 10,

20, 30, 40 and 50 µg/ml. The calibration curve was plotted between 10-50 µg/ml concentration range.

c) Precision

The precision of the developed method was determined by analysed the concentration of 20 µg/ml Igaratimod solution for six times on the same day. The % RSD value was calculated.

d) Accuracy

In the pre-analysed sample, the standard Igaratimod solution was spiked at three different levels such as 50 %, 100 % and 150 % and those were made upto the required volumes with the diluent. The peak area of all peaks of each levels was measured at 258 nm. The % recovery was calculated.

e) LOD & LOQ

There were several approaches for determining LOD and LOQ and that was depend upon whether the procedure was instrumental or non-instrumental. The LOD and LOQ were calculated by,

$$\text{LOD} = \frac{3.3 \times \text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Slope}}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = \frac{10 \times \text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Slope}}$$

f) Robustness

Robustness of the proposed method was determined by slightly changed the parameters and observed their effects. The % RSD was calculated for each separate parameters. Changing the parameters like,

- Wavelengths ± 1 nm
- Flowrate ± 0.1 ml/min
- Mobile phase ratio ± 1 or 2 ml of solvents

The selected conditions for each parameters are as follows,

- For wavelength = 257 nm, 258 nm and 259 nm were selected.

- For flowrate = 0.9 ml/min, 1 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min were selected.
- For mobile phase (MeOH: ACN: Water) ratio=32:29:39, 30:30:40 and 28:31:41% v/v/v were selected.

g) Ruggedness

The Ruggedness of the proposed method was determined by two different analyst and two instruments using same operational and environmental conditions for analysing the 20 µg/ml concentration of Igaratimod.

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES ^[15-19]

The Forced degradation studies of Standard was very important for understanding the stability and degradation pathway of the Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API). These degradation studies helpful for better knowledge about the chemical behaviour of API and support the development of stability-indicating profile of the drug. The most important considerations in the drug discovery were related to safety, not only for the drug but also for impurities and degraded products present in them. Impurities present in the drug may lead to cytotoxicity, carcinogenic or teratogenic effects. The amount of impurities was very low for prolonged exposure to them may be very hazardous. Hence, identification and the checking for the degradants very crucial and essential. Drug degradation profiles important for monitoring the stable formulation and provide appropriate drug shelf-life valuation. Structural description of impurities and degradation products in bulk API has become an integral part of pharmaceutical product development. In this research work, raw material Igaratimod was subjected to stress conditions like acidic, basic, hydrolytic, oxidative, reduction. Photolytic, thermal and UV light.

The working stock solution was 100 µg/ml.

Acid Degradation Study

To evaluate acid-induced degradation, 2 ml of the working stock solution was transferred into a clean 10 ml volumetric flask, followed by the addition of 1 ml of 0.1 N sulfuric acid. The mixture was allowed to stand undisturbed for 24 hours. Subsequently, 1 ml of

0.1 N potassium hydroxide was added to neutralized the solution. The final volume was adjusted with diluent. The sample was then injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to analyse any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

Base Degradation Study

For base degradation, 2 ml of the stock solution was transferred into a clean 10 ml volumetric flask. To this, 1 ml of 0.1 N potassium hydroxide was added, and the mixture was kept undisturbed for 24 hours to induce degradation. It was then neutralized with 1 ml of 0.1 N sulfuric acid, and the volume was adjusted with diluent. The sample was injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to analyse any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

Hydrolytic Degradation Study

In hydrolytic degradation testing, 2 ml of the stock solution was transferred into a 10 ml clean volumetric flask, followed by the addition of 3 mL of HPLC-grade water to initiate degradation. After 24 hours, the solution was diluted with diluent. Subsequently, 1 ml of this solution was transferred into another 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with diluent. Samples were withdrawn and analyzed by injecting into th HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to verify if any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

Oxidative Degradation Study

For oxidative stress testing, 2 ml of the stock solution was introduced into a clean 10 ml volumetric flask, followed by the addition of 1 ml of 0.3 % hydrogen peroxide. The solution was left to stand for 24 hours, then diluted to volume with diluent and mixed thoroughly. The sample was analyzed by injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to check if any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

Reduction Degradation Study

In the reduction study, 2 ml of the stock solution was pipetted into a 10 ml clean volumetric flask. Degradation was initiated by the addition of 1 ml of 10% sodium bisulfate solution. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours, followed by dilution with diluent up to the mark. The sample was collected and analyzed by injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to analyse any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

Photolytic Degradation Study

A weighed quantity (25 mg) of Igaratimod was exposed to direct sunlight for 4 hours. Prepared the stock solution by used the exposed drug, 2 ml of the resulting stock solution was transferred into a clean 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with diluent. The sample was analyzed by injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to check if any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

Thermal Degradation Study

To assess thermal degradation, 25 mg of Igaratimod was exposed to an oven temperature ranging between 70°C for 24 hours. Afterwards, 2 ml of the resulting stock solution was transferred into a 10 ml clean volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with diluent. The sample was analyzed by injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to verify if any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition..

UV Degradation Study

A 25 mg quantity of Igaratimod was exposed to UV light for 24 hours. From the resultant solution, 2 ml was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with diluent. The prepared sample was analyzed by injecting into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatogram was recorded to check if any degradation peaks may formed during stress condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selection of Analytical wavelength

UV Spectrum for Igratimod (10 µg/ml) in the selected diluent (mobile phase) was scanned between the wavelengths 400 – 200 nm. The absorbance maximum of Igratimod was found as 258 nm. The Spectrum was shown in Figure 2.

Figure- 2 UV Spectrum of Igratimod at 258 nm

In method development, RP-HPLC method was used for determination of Igratimod with optimized chromatographic conditions to produce sharp chromatographic peak with less retention time. Trials were conducted to develop the method for Igratimod determination. Various mobile phase ratios and diluents were experimented for getting optimized chromatogram with satisfied retention time. The mobile phase selection was done by polarity of the functional group present in Igratimod. During the method development, the column selected based on tailing factor, theoretical plate number and shape of the peak. And finally, the mobile phase chosen was MeOH:ACN; Water in the ratio of 30:30:40 % v/v/v and the same mobile phase was used as diluent for the drug with the flowrate was 1 ml/min. the Shimadzu C₁₈ column (4.6×250 mm, 5 µm) chosen as stationary phase for this chromatographic analysis. All this conditions gives perfect chromatographic peak and that was eluted with satisfied retention time. The elution time of Igratimod was found as 4.042 mins. The chromatographic peaks of blank and optimized peak of Igratimod was shown in Figure 3 & 4.

Figure-3: Blank Chromatogram

Figure-4: Optimized Chromatogram Of Igratimod

Method Validation:

System suitability

Standard of Igratimod was subjected for six time analyses to obtain their corresponding chromatograms. The System suitability parameters shown in the Table-3.

Table-3: System Suitability Parameters Of Igratimod

Parameters	Limit	Result
Capacity factor	≤ 1	0.7566
Number of theoretical plates	>2000	2920.3216
Tailing factor	≤ 2	1.091
Retention time	-	4.042

Linearity

The series of five concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 µg/ml) were prepared for Igratimod and the calibration curve was plotted between concentration and peak area. From the calibration data, the

regression equation was obtained as $y = 77168x + 12003$. The correlation coefficient (r^2) value was found as 0.9999. There were good correlation throughout this concentration range 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The calibration curve was shown in Figure-5 and results are provided in Table-4.

Figure-5: Calibration Curve Of Igratimod

Table-4: Linearity Data Of Igratimod

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
10	788199
20	1559953
30	2331274
40	3118411
50	3849360

Precision

The six times sample injection of Igratimod (20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were analysed and results were recorded. The Percentage purity, Standard deviation and % RSD were calculated. The chromatogram of sample was shown in Figure-6 and the results of precision were presented in Table-5.

Figure-6: Sample Chromatogram

Table-5: Precision Data For Igratimod (20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Sl. No	Peak area	% Purity (%)	S.D*	% RSD*
1	1548644	100.24	0.4903	0.4909
2	1548644	100.24		
3	1538310	99.52		
4	1535991	99.36		
5	1546155	99.40		
6	1552198	100.44		
AVERAGE % PURITY		99.86 %		

*Mean of 6 observations

Accuracy

The results for 50, 100 and 150 % of recovery studies were analysed and recorded. In the results, amount recovered, % amount recovery, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated. The chromatograms for 50 %, 100 % and 150 % were shown in Figure-7,8 and 9 respectively. The data of precision were presented in Table-6.

Figure-7: Accuracy (50 %)

Figure-8: Accuracy (100 %)

Figure-9: Accuracy (150 %)

Table-6: Accuracy Data For Igaratimod

% Conc.	Amount present (µg/ml)	Amount Added (µg/ml)	Amount Estimated* (µg/ml)	Amount Recovered* (µg/ml)	% Recovery*	S.D*	% RSD*
50	20	10	30.02	10.02	100.20	0.8888	0.8870
100	20	20	40.255	20.255	101.27	0.0057	0.0056
150	20	30	49.726	29.726	99.08	0.0057	0.0057

*Mean of 3 observations

LOD & LOQ

The values of standard deviation and slope value from the calibration curve were substituted in the respective formulas of both LOD and LOQ. The results of LOD & LOQ were shown in Table-7.

Table-7: Lod & Loq Data For Igaratimod

LOD (µg/ml)	1.2188
LOQ (µg/ml)	3.6933

Robustness

The Robustness of the developed method was confirmed by conducting the analysis under deliberate changes includes change in wavelengths, flowrate and mobile phase ratios. The % RSD for each conditions were calculated. The results were shown in Table-8.

Table-8: Robustness Data For Igaratimod

Sl.no	Conditions	S.D*	% RSD*
1	Wavelength 259 nm	99.77	0.4085
2	Wavelength 257 nm	100.50	0.3585
3	Flow rate 0.9 ml/min	100.01	0.1973
4	Flow rate 1.1 ml/min	99.57	0.0461
5	Mobile phase (32:29:39)	99.74	0.4150
6	Mobile phase (28:31:41)	99.73	0.4687

*Mean of 3 observations

Ruggedness

The Ruggedness of the developed method was determined by performing the analysing of samples

by two different analysts and two instruments. The % RSD were calculated for each parameters. The datas were shown in Table-9.

Table-9: Ruggedness Data For Igaratimod

Parameters	Percentage Purity (%)*	S.D*	% RSD*
Analyst 1	99.85	0.0018	0.00180
Analyst 2	99.33	0.2274	0.2289
Instrument 1	99.58	0.1285	0.1290
Instrument 2	99.68	0.2498	0.2506

*Mean of 3 observations

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES

In Forced degradation studies, the stability of the drug (Igaratimod) were studied under different stress conditions like acid, base, hydrolytic, oxidative, reduction, photolytic, thermal and UV light. The data

obtained from this study do not shows any extra peaks and that confirms the drug Igaratimod were stable under all stress conditions throughout the study period. Hence, there was no interference or degradants present in the Igaratimod. The Degradation related data was shown in Table-10.

Table-10: Degradation Data Of Igaratimod

Stress Condition	Time	% Degradation
0.1 N Sulphuric Acid	24 hrs	Not degraded
0.1 N Potassium Hydroxide	24 hrs	Not degraded
HPLC grade water	24 hrs	Not degraded
0.3 % Hydrogen Peroxide	24 hrs	Not degraded
10 % Sodium bisulfate	24 hrs	Not degraded
Sunlight	04 hrs	Not degraded
Hot air oven	24 hrs	Not degraded
UV- Light	24 hrs	Not degraded

Figure-12: Hydrolytic Degradation Study Of Iguratimod

Figure-15: Photolytic Degradation Study Of Iguratimod

Figure-13: Oxidation Degradation Study Of Iguratimod

Figure-16: Thermal Degradation Study Of Iguratimod

Figure-14: Reduction Degradation Study Of Iguratimod

Figure-17: Uv Light Degradation Study Of Iguratimod

Table- 11: Advantages Of Developed Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Methods For Iguratimod

Points to be noted	Advantage
Novelty	RP-HPLC method was developed for the drug by using this mobile phase composition(methanol:acetonitrile:water)
Linearity Correlation co-efficient (R^2)	0.9999
Diluent	Mobile phase was used as an diluent
Specificity	There is no interference from excipients

Stability- indicating advantage	There was no degradants was found in Iguratimod under different stress conditions
Accuracy & Precision	High recovery power and low % RSD values
Cost-efficient	The developed method utilized readily available solvents
Eco-friendly	Buffer free system
Industrial applicability	Simple, reproducibility and utilized for routine quality control of Iguratimod

CONCLUSION

A simple, precise and accurate RP-HPLC Stability-Indicating method was successfully developed for the estimation of Iguratimod in both Bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form and the method was validated as per ICH Q2(R1). The maximum absorbance of Iguratimod in diluent was 258 nm by using Shimadzu C₁₈ Column. The chromatographic conditions includes isocratic mode of elution, Methanol: Acetonitrile: Water as mobile phase in the ratio of 30:30:40 % v/v/v with flowrate 1 ml/min. These optimized chromatographic conditions made the Iguratimod peak sharper with satisfied analyte retention. The developed method was validated by using the validation parameters like system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD, LOQ, robustness and ruggedness. The results obtained from the validation parameters confirms the method was reproducible, robust and reliable. The forced degradation studies were carried by using acid, base, hydrolytic, oxidative, reduction, photolytic, thermal and UV light. The degradation study helps in confirming the stability of Iguratimod in all these stress conditions throughout study period. The developed method was simple, precise, robust, rapid and highly reproducible. Hence, the method was well suited for stability studies and for routine quality control analysis of Iguratimod in both Bulk and Tablet dosage form.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declared none.

REFERENCES

1. Rao BV, Sowjanya GN, Ajitha A, Uma V and Rao M. A review on stability indicating HPLC method development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2015;4(8):405-423.
2. S. P. Kumbhar*, S. S. Patil, C. V. Panchal and P. M. Jadhav. Development and Validation of Reverse Phase-High-Performance Liquid Chromatography Method for Nebivolol. *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.* 2024;2(5):673-680.
3. United State Pharmacopeia, USP 29/NF 24, US Pharmacopeial Convention, Inc, Rockville MD, 2006:555-556, 1777, 1861, 3050- 3052.
4. Andrew F. Studied simultaneous analysis of Escitalopram and bupropion-SR by High Performance Liquid Spectroscopy.
5. Hanretta D. Studied determination of Escitalopram, with Duloxetine and Olanzapine by reversed phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography.
6. Elham A. Studied Micelle Enhanced Fluorimetric and Thin Layer Chromatography Densitometric Methods for the Determination of (±) Citalopram and its S – Enantiomer Escitalopram.
7. Christine Greiner. Studied Determination of citalopram and escitalopram together with their active main metabolites desmethyl(es)citalopram in human serum by column- switching high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and spectrophotometric detection.
8. ICH guidelines, analytical method validation (Q3). Geneva, July 2000.
9. Guidance for industry, Analytical Procedure and Method Validation, U. S. Department of Health and Human Services FDA, Aug 2000.
10. Mrinalini C. Damle* and Shital P. Ghode. Determination of Iguratimod in Human plasma by HPLC method. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018;7(14):404-413.

11. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pound/IguratomodFD#SectionTop>
12. Damle MC and Ghode SP. Determination of Iguratomod in human plasma by HPLC method. *World J Pharm Res*, 2018;7(14):404-13.
13. Ravindra Bhaskar Nehete and Pushendra Sharma. Analytical method development and validation of cleaning methodology for residual determination of Iguratomod. *International Journal of Current Advanced Research*. 2018;7(2(C)):9746-9754.
14. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) of technical requirements for the registration of Pharmaceuticals for human use, validation of Analytical procedures methodology; ICH Q(R1), Geneva; 1996:1-8.
15. Lamiaa AH, Al-Ghobashy MA and Samah SA. Evaluation of the pattern and kinetics of degradation of adalimumab using a stability-indicating orthogonal testing protocol. *Biomedical Chromatography* 2019;4676: 1-13.
16. Khagga Bhavyasri, Chejati Mounika and M Sumakanth. Method development, validation and forced degradation studies for determination of tigecycline in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form using UV spectroscopy. *Journal of young pharmacist*. 2020;12(2); 63-66.
17. Ramalingam Peraman, K.V. Lalitha, Nga Mallikarjuna Raja B and Hari Babu Routhu. Identification of degradation products and a stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of flupritine maleate in pharmaceutical dosage forms. *Sci Pharm*. 2014;82:281-293.
18. Pridhvi krishna gaddey and Raja Sundararajan. Development of a Stability Indicating UPLC Method for the Determination of Tirbanibulin in Bulk and Its Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. 2024;21(1):25-35.
19. Patel Seema A*, Sayyed Nazifa, Mobina I, Manjra Mehfuza U, Aejaz Ahmed and G.J.Khan. An Eco-friendly RP-HPLC and UV-Method Development and Validation for an Estimation of Tolvaptan in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form followed by Forced Degradation Studies. *JPRI*. 2021;33(42B):271-286.

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